

Mean and Variance of Mathematical Expectation and Frequency Distribution

Chinnaraji Annamalai
 School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
 Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Addition theorem on Expectations: The mathematical expectation of the sum of independent random variables is equal to the sum of their expectations. For any two of independent random variables X and Y ,

$$E(X + Y) = E(X) + E(Y).$$

Multiplication theorem on Expectations: The mathematical expectation of the product of independent random variables is equal to the product of their expectations. For any two of independent random variables X and Y ,

$$E(XY) = E(X)E(Y).$$

Frequency Distribution

The frequency distribution $(x, f(x))$ of the random variable X is shown by the following table. The frequency distribution table [1, 2] is a comprehensive way of representing the organization of raw data of a quantitative variable.

$X:$	x_1	x_2	x_3	\dots	\dots	\dots	x_n
$f:$	f_1	f_2	f_3	\dots	\dots	\dots	f_n

Sum of frequencies: $N = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i = f_1 + f_2 + f_3 + \dots + f_n.$

$$\text{Mean } (\bar{X}) = \bar{x} = \mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i = \frac{f_1 x_1 + f_2 x_2 + f_3 x_3 + \dots + f_n x_n}{N}.$$

$$\text{Mathematical expectation } E(X) = \bar{X} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i.$$

$$\text{Variance } (\sigma_x^2) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i^2 - \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i \right)^2.$$

Proof. Let prove the variance using short-cut method.

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = E[X - \bar{X}]^2 = E[X - \mu]^2 = E(E^2 - 2X\mu + \mu^2).$$

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = E(E^2) - 2\mu E(X) + \mu^2, (\because E(X + Y) = E(X) + E(Y)).$$

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x_i - \bar{x})^2 = E(E^2) - 2\mu \times \mu + \mu^2 = E(E^2) - \mu^2 = E(E^2) - [E(X)]^2.$$

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x_i - \bar{x})^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i^2 - \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i \right)^2.$$

Hence proved.

Let us find the solution for a **real-life problem** below:

Find the mean, variance, and standard deviation for the following data:

Height in cms	70-75	75-80	80-85	85-90	90-95	95-100	100-105	105-110	110-115
No. of Children	3	4	7	7	15	9	6	6	3

Solution:

Class Interval	Frequency f_i	Mid-Point x_i	$y_i = \frac{x_i - A}{h}$	y_i^2	$f_i y_i$	$f_i y_i^2$
70-75(h=5)	3	72.5	-4	16	-12	48
75-80	4	77.5	-3	9	-12	36
80-85	7	82.5	-2	4	-14	28
85-90	7	87.5	-1	1	-7	7
90-95	15	92.5 (A)	0	0	0	0
95-100	9	97.5	1	1	9	9
100-105	6	102.5	2	4	12	24
105-110	6	107.5	3	9	18	54
110-115	3	112.5	4	16	12	48
$N = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i = 60$					$\sum_{i=1}^n f_i y_i = 6$	$\sum_{i=1}^n f_i y_i^2 = 254$

$$\text{Mean } (\bar{x}) = A + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i y_i}{N} \times h = 92.5 + \frac{6}{60} \times 5 = 92.5 + 0.5 = 93.$$

$$\text{Variance } (\sigma^2) = \frac{h^2}{N^2} \left[N \sum_{i=1}^n f_i y_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n f_i y_i \right)^2 \right] = \frac{5^2}{60^2} [60 \times 254 - 6^2] = 105.58.$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = \sqrt{105.58} = 10.27.$$

Mean and variance of a dataset

For a dataset with n values $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$, the mean, variance, and standard deviation are given below:

$$\text{Mean } (\mu) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}; \text{ Variance } (\sigma^2) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu)^2}{n}; \text{ and SD } (\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu)^2}{n}}.$$

Example: Find the mean, variance, and standard deviation of first n natural numbers.

$$\text{Mean } (\bar{x}) = \frac{1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n}{n} = \frac{1}{n} \times \frac{n(n+1)}{2} = \frac{(n+1)}{2}, \left(\because \sum_{k=1}^n k = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \right).$$

$$\text{Variance } (\sigma^2) = \frac{\sum x_i^2}{n} - (\bar{x})^2 = \frac{\sum n^2}{n} - (\bar{x})^2, \text{ where } \sum_{k=1}^n k^2 = \frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6}.$$

$$\text{Variance } (\sigma^2) = \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6} \right) - \frac{(n+1)^2}{4} = \frac{n^2 - 1}{12}.$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{n^2 - 1}{3}}.$$

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2024) Mathematical Expectations on Frequency and Probability Distributions. Zenodo Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14190921>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2024) The Gaussian Integral for the Normal Distribution in Machine Learning. *Cambridge Open Engage, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2024-p4j6k>.